

Reaction of 4-Bromo-2-pyrazolines with Fluorene : Synthesis of 9,9'-Bipyrazolinyl-fluorene

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The attachment of a pyrazole ring in an organic structure is of significant interest because of its easy accessibility and diverse properties that are associated with it. The selection of pyrazole derivatives in the field of clinical medicine is undoubtedly the principal practical application that one can come across because of their considerable bacteriostatic, bactericidal and fungicidal actions¹. The study of light dependent toxicity of non-carcinogenic polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons on aqueous organisms has been reported². Further, bromo and iodo derivative of *N*-ethyl-9-fluorenylamine are shown to be antiadrenaline and antinoradrenaline agents³.

Results and Discussion

13,5-Triaryl-4-bromo-2-pyrazolines (2) can be prepared conveniently⁴ from easily available chalcone dibromides (1) by reacting it with hydrazine and substituted hydrazines. The structure of these series of compounds were established on the basis of their ir and ¹H nmr spectra. The assignment of the *cis*-relationship of the 4-bromine atom with respect to the 5-hydrogen in compound 2 was further confirmed on the basis of their difficulty in the elimination of HBr with triethylamine.

Fluorene (pK_a = 22.6)⁵ carbanion (generated *in situ*) is expected to react with these bromo compounds to form the 9-monopyrazolinyl compounds. In the event, it was observed experimentally that the mono-substituted fluorene carbanion (generated *in situ*) reacted further with additional unit of pyrazoline following the nucleophilic displacement to 4.

The formation of 9-dialkyl(or aryl)fluorene was reported earlier⁶. It was suggested that 9-monosubstituted fluorene is more acidic than 9-C-H unsubstituted fluorene^{7,8}. Further, it was reported⁸ that polar solvents assist in the formation of the disubstituted product, because of the solubility of the organometallic intermediate formed during the course of the reaction.

A close examination of ¹H nmr spectra of these compounds revealed the presence of sharp singlet around δ 4.5–5.0 indicating the presence of Ar-CH system in addition to the multiplet observed at δ 7–8 due to the bulk aromatic protons⁹. The absence of any other high field singlet sig-

nal substantiated that the initially formed adduct, 3 undergoes rapid isomerisation to the structure 4 whose structure was further confirmed by ir and elemental analyses.

Ar, Ar' = Ph,
p-ClC₆H₄, *m*-NO₂C₆H₄,
p-OCH₃C₆H₄

- 2a, Ar = Ar' = Ph, R = H, b; Ar = Ph, Ar' = *p*-ClC₆H₄, R = H,
c; Ar = Ph, Ar' = *m*-NO₂C₆H₄, R = H; d, Ar = Ph, Ar' = *p*-OCH₃C₆H₄,
R = H,
e; Ar = *p*-ClC₆H₄, Ar' = Ph, R = H, f; Ar = *m*-NO₂C₆H₄, Ar' = Ph,
R = H,
g; Ar = Ar' = R = Ph; h; Ar = R = Ph, Ar' = *p*-ClC₆H₄,
i; Ar = *p*-ClC₆H₄, Ar' = R = Ph,
j; Ar = *m*-NO₂C₆H₄, Ar' = R = Ph

- 4a; Ar = Ar' = Ph, R = H,
b; Ar = Ph, Ar' = *p*-ClC₆H₄, R = H,
c; Ar = Ph, Ar' = *m*-NO₂C₆H₄,
R = H,
d; Ar = *p*-ClC₆H₄, Ar' = Ph, R = H,
e; Ar = Ar' = R = Ph; f; Ar = R = Ph,
Ar' = *p*-ClC₆H₄

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3) were determined on a Varian EM spectrometer 390 (90 MHz) using TMS as internal standard.

1,3,5-Trisubstituted-4-bromo-2-pyrazolines (2) : General procedure : To a refluxing solution of 1,3-diaryl-2,3-dibromo-1-propanone (1; 0.03 mol) in absolute ethanol (160 ml) or ethanol-benzene mixture (2 : 1; 240 ml) was added hydrazine hydrate (85%) or substituted hydrazine (0.03 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h on a steam-bath. The solution was then kept cooled at 0° overnight. The separated solids were crystallised from ethanol, (yield : 50–90%) : **2a**, m.p. 146° ; **b**, 181° ; **c**, 147° ; **d**, 101° ; **e**, 184° ; **f**, 143° ; **g**, 128° ; **h**, 165° ; **i**, 163° ; **j**, 135° .

Reaction of substituted-4-bromopyrazolines (2) with fluorene carbanion. Synthesis of 4. General procedure : To a stirred suspension of sodium ethoxide (generated *in situ* from metallic sodium and absolute ethanol); fluorene (0.166 g, 0.001 mol) was added and agitated. Then, 4-bromopyrazoline (0.001 mol) was added to the mixture and stirred for additional 2–3 h. The precipitated solid was filtered out. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure, excess water added and subsequently acidified. The resulting solids were washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (yield : 32–78%) : **4a**, m.p. 96° ; **b**, 71° ; **c**, 98° ; **d**, 111° ; **e**, 61° ; **f**, 64° .

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